

AM27

WATER QUALITY INDEX OF COASTAL SYSTEMS BASED ON MACROALGAE SPECIES

Ardila-Poveda, Leidy Solange¹; Siqueiros-Beltrones, David A.². Centro Interdisciplinario de Ciencias Marinas - Instituto Politécnico Nacional, 1) Departamento de Biotecnología; 2) Departamento de Plancton y Ecología Marina. La Paz, 23090; México. lsardilap@gmail.com, dsiquei@ipn.mx.

Keywords: Bioindicator, seaweed, pollution

Introduction. Macroalgae respond to the variation of the environment. Especially, the change in temperature produces different floristics (taxocoenoses) as has been observed over time in coastal systems of Baja California Sur. Other physicochemical changes (salinity, pH, dissolved oxygen) and concentration of nutrients (nitrate, phosphate, and silicate), as well as metals concentrated in water, influence species composition. Depending on the composition and production of polysaccharides in the intracellular matrix of each species of macroalgae, can be found to a greater or lesser minerals content. This will depend on the chemical affinity of the mineral with the polysaccharide; as well as, the chemical species of the mineral and its valence state. Other conditions intervene in this relationship, especially the pH and dissolved oxygen in the water, which can drastically affect the formation of compounds that in some cases can be highly toxic.

The objective was to create a water quality indicator for coastal systems of Baja California Sur using macroalgae species.

Methods. The distribution of 78 species of macroalgae (Guisande 2013) from a registered taxonomic list for Baja California Sur in the Global Biodiversity Information Facility database (Siqueiros-Beltrones et al. 2017) was studied. The average values and standard error (range) of each of the physicochemical characteristics pH, salinity (unitless) dissolved oxygen (ml/L) and nutrient concentration ($\mu\text{mol/L}$ of NO_3 , SO_4 and PO_4) of seawater from 2005 to 2012 of the National Oceanic Atmospheric Administration NOAA (Garcia et al. 2013a b; Zweng et al. 2013) were gathered, and were compared between species, in function on the increase of the variable in the water.

Results. For the water quality index, species with wide tolerance intervals were chosen to establish them as "passive monitors" of the mineral content, as well as species that occur at narrow intervals of variation, which would indicate a certain state of the quality of the water. It also proposes possible taxocoenoses that can occur in Baja California Sur warning on specific water conditions and would indicate the quality status. The brown algae of BCS studied were shown to be not very tolerant, especially with temperature increase, which is why they

develop mainly in temperate waters. The changes in dissolved oxygen, pH, dissolved organic matter and silicates in the water were the variables with the greatest contribution to the association of species by habitat similarity.

Conclusions. The variation of water quality in terms of physico-chemical characteristics and nutrient concentration causes distinct macroalgal taxocoenoses in coastal systems, the specific composition can at the same time determine the water quality status. It can be observed that the possible associations reflect situations found in the theory of intermediate disturbance (Roxburgh et al. 2004) where the greatest diversity of species were found within average values of nutrient concentration. As well as the smallest number of species, there will be coastal waters with very low degrees of disturbance or with very high values, given that few species have tolerances in extreme values. A larger number of species survive at lower concentrations of salinity and nutrients than at higher concentrations, so the established upper limits are usually critical for most of the macroalgae species studied in Baja California Sur.

Acknowledgments. The first author received scholarship funds from Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología Conacyt, for her post-graduate studies in CICIMAR.

References

- Guisande C (2013) *ModestR Software User's Manual*. 36:1202–1207.
- Siqueiros-Beltrones D, Ramos Rivera P, Careaga-Olivera S (2017) *Macroalgas marinas de Baja California Sur Parte I: Bahía de la Paz y Bahía de la Ventana*. GBIF. Data occurrence. Accessed 20 Mar 2018
- García H, Locarnini T, Boyer J, Antonov O, Baranova M, Zweng J, Reagan D, Johnson R, 2014. World Ocean Atlas 2013, Volume 4: Dissolved Inorganic Nutrients (phosphate, nitrate, silicate). S. Levitus, Ed., A. Mishonov Technical Ed.; NOAA Atlas NESDIS 76, 25 pp.
- García H, Locarnini T, Boyer J, Antonov O, Baranova M, Zweng J, Reagan, D and Johnson R. 2014. World Ocean Atlas 2013, Volume 3: Dissolved Oxygen, Apparent Oxygen Utilization, and Oxygen Saturation. S. Levitus, Ed., A. Mishonov Technical Ed.; NOAA Atlas NESDIS 75, 27 pp.
- Zweng M, Reagan J, Antonov J, et al (2013) Volume 2: Salinity. World Ocean Atlas 2013, NOAA Atlas NESDIS 74, p 27.
- Roxburgh S, Shea K, Wilson B (2004) The intermediate disturbance hypothesis: patch dynamics and mechanisms of species coexistence. *Ecol.* 85:359–371.

AM28

PHYLOGENETIC ANALYSIS BY DNA BARCODE OF SEA TURTLES

Fátima Y. Camacho-Sánchez¹, Hervey Rodríguez-González³, Alan A. Zavala-Norzagaray⁴, José A. Narváez-Zapata², Héctor H. Acosta-Acosta⁵, Miguel Angel Reyes-López¹

¹Conservation Medicine Lab., ²Biología Industrial, Centro de Biología Genómica-Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Reynosa, Tamaulipas. MEX., C. P. 88700. ³Lab. Nutrición Acuícola, Depto. de Acuicultura, ⁴Lab. Vida Silvestre, Depto. Medio Ambiente CIIDIR Sinaloa-Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Guasave, Sinaloa. MEX., C. P. 81000. ⁵Comisión Nacional de Áreas Naturales Protegidas, Cd. Victoria, Tamps., MEX., C. P. 87000.

Key words: Barcode, COI, Lepidochelys kempii

Introduction. DNA barcoding is a system that uses short sequence instead of whole genome; therefore, it makes ecological or biological system more accessible. Cytochrome c oxidase subunit I gene, offers the solution to quickly distinguish among species, providing information on species diversification and molecular evolution (1). Sea turtles occupied several ecosystems through their highly migratory and threatened worldwide; we should take conservation measures for their study such as molecular tools by DNA barcoding (2). Six out of 7 worldwide sea turtles nest in Mexico, all of them are grouped in 2 known families, Dermochelidae (*Dermochelys coriacea*) and Cheloniidae (*Lepidochelys kempii*, *L. olivacea*, *Caretta caretta*, *Eretmochelys imbricata*, *Chelonia mydas*) (3).

The objective of this work is to analyze reported and generated sequences from COI gene to make the first described database about it and to compare genetic variability among sea turtles worldwide.

Methods. One hundred and fifty-six sea turtle sequences were compared in total, 143 were download from BOLD and 13 sequences obtained *in vitro* were compared; afterwards, those ones assigned to similar groups and transformed into FASTA format, then a nucleotide alignment was made by ClustalW to obtain haplotype networks by Network 5 and finally a Neighbor joining tree was constructed by MEGA 7 with 10,000 replicates, using nucleotide substitution model of K2p (4).

Results. Thirty-five haplotypes were separated in different networks for each species, due to the variation between nucleotides and to 670 mutations found in total for all the sequences (Fig. 1). The average distance was 8.2% and the average distance between the families Dermochelidae and Cheloniidae was 8.1%. The average distance between Cheloniidae was 6.6% (Table 1).

Table 1. Mean divergence of the sequences (K2p) within the species (underlined number) and between pairs of marine turtle species.

	Lk	Cc	Cm	Dc	Ei	Lo	Nd
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i> (Lk)	<u>0.00</u>						
<i>Caretta caretta</i> (Cc)	0.06	<u>0.01</u>					
<i>Chelonia mydas</i> (Cm)	0.08	0.09	<u>0.00</u>				
<i>Dermochelys coriacea</i> (Dc)	0.08	0.12	0.14	<u>0.00</u>			
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i> (Ei)	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.03	<u>0.03</u>		
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i> (Lo)	0.02	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.09	<u>0.00</u>	
<i>Natator depressus</i> (Nd)	0.09	0.09	0.07	0.10	0.10	0.06	<u>0.00</u>

Fig. 1. Haplotypes Network of the COI gene (mtDNA) for sea turtles. Each of the colors represents each species of sea turtles.

Conclusions. The COI fragment is variable in sea turtle taxa. In general, haplotypes were not interspecifically shared in all samples analyzed. The DNA barcode based on the COI gene identifies each species of sea turtles and to become a useful tool for determining intra and inter species variability of the world's marine turtles. Particularly, the nucleotide sequences reported in BOLD from *L. kempii* (Kemp's ridley) were compared with 3 sequences obtained *in vitro*, 100% all ones were aligned and clustered in the same haplotype. In the end, this work set up the first database for sea turtles worldwide by the study of mitochondrial COI gene.

Acknowledgements. To CONACYT and BEIFI-IPN for the scholarships granted, as well as IPN for the support in the SIP project: 20161179 and 20171851. Thank you to all the people from Rancho Nuevo, Tam., and CONANP-SEMARNAT

References.

- 1.- Hebert, P. D. N., Cywinska, A., Ball, S. L., & deWaard, J. R. (2003). Biological identifications through DNA barcodes. *Proceedings. Biological Sciences / The Royal Society*, 270(1512), 313–21.
- 2.- Naro-Maciel, E., Reid, B., Fitzsimmons, N. N., Le, M., Desalle, R. & Amato, G. (2010). DNA barcodes for globally threatened marine turtles: A registry approach to documenting biodiversity. *Molecular Ecology Resources*, 10(2), 252–263.
- 3.- Vargas, S. M., Araujo, F. C. F., & Santos, F. R. (2009). DNA barcoding of Brazilian sea turtles (Testudines) AN - prod.academic_MSTAR_21050128; 11319878. *Genetics and Molecular Biology*, 32, 608–612.
- 4.- Kumar, S., Stecher, G., & Tamura, K. (2016). MEGA7: Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis Version 7.0 for Bigger Datasets. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 33(7), 1870–1874.